

Stability Constants and Thermodynamic Parameters of Iron(II) Chelates with 2-(Phenylhydrazino)propionic Acid and Their Substituted Derivatives in Aqueous-Ethanol Medium

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The stability constants of Fe^{2+} complexes with 2-(Xphenylhydrazino)propionic acids (X = -H, *p*-CH₃, *p*-NO₂ and *o*-CH₃) have been studied with a view to understand the effect of various substitutions present in the ligands. The studies have been carried out potentiometrically in ethanol-water (40% v/v) medium using Calvin-Bjerrum pH-titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti. Thermodynamic parameters have been evaluated and discussed. The effect of dielectric constant on the formation constants has been studied.

THE compounds of substituted phenylhydrazones of pyruvic acid have immense biological and analytical applications^{1,2}. Recently, we reported³ the formation constants of 2-(phenylhydrazino)propionic acid and its substituted compounds with Mn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Zn^{2+} . The thermodynamic parameters associated with the complexation were evaluated and discussed to explain the nature of bonding. In the present paper results obtained on the proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants of 2-(phenylhydrazino)propionic acid, 2-(*p*-tolylhydrazino)propionic acid, 2-(*p*-nitrophenylhydrazino)propionic acid and 2-(*o*-tolylhydrazino)propionic acid with Fe^{2+} in various ionic strengths, temperatures and in different ethanol-water mixtures (v/v) employing Calvin-Bjerrum^{4,5} pH-titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁶. In the presence of Fe^{2+} , the stability constants were found to be higher than those of the other transition metal ions studied earlier under similar conditions except Cu^{2+} . From the formation constants obtained at various temperatures the thermodynamic parameters such as ΔH^\ddagger , ΔG^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger have been evaluated and separated into their corresponding electrostatic (ΔG_e^\ddagger and ΔH_e^\ddagger) and non-electrostatic or cratic (ΔG_c^\ddagger and ΔH_c^\ddagger) components with a view to understand the extent of ionic and covalent nature of the complexes. An attempt has been made to investigate the effect of variation in dielectric constant on the stabilities of complexes in various ethanol-water mixtures.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were either B.D.H. (A.R.) or Merck (G.R.) reagents. The ligands employed were synthesised in our laboratory by known methods⁷⁻¹⁰. As the solubility of the ligands is low in water, the solutions were prepared in 40% (v/v) ethanol-water media. The methods employed

to determine the formation constants and the preparation of ferrous nitrate solution in the present work were described in an earlier paper¹¹. Since the titrations were carried out in ethanol-water media appropriate pH corrections were applied to the experimentally observed values¹².

Results and Discussion

The proton dissociation constant of the ligands (pK_a) and stepwise stability constants $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were calculated using the half-integral method. The stability constants were also evaluated by pointwise and least-square methods and they agree within error limits to that of half-integral method and have been presented in Table 1. Fe^{2+} chelates of the ligands showed high stabilities indicating the derivation from the natural order. Similar observations were reported by several workers¹³⁻¹⁵ in their study on a number of ligands like 4-hydroxyptoridine, folic acid, riboflavin, pyridine-2-aldoxime, *o*-phenanthroline, bipyridyl, terpyridyl, etc. A unique feature in all these compounds is that they contain one, two or three tertiary nitrogens. The unusual high stability of Fe^{2+} chelates were also noted by Irving and Williams¹⁶ and they attributed to the resonance orbital stabilization energy of Fe^{2+} complexes upon coordination with a ligand having an aromatic ring system. In the present investigation the ligands possess an aromatic ring system and a tertiary nitrogen which might be responsible for the observed high stabilities.

Effect of ionic strength: To investigate the nature of interactions between the metal ion and ligands the metal-ligand stability constant values were determined at 0.01, 0.05 and 0.1 M ionic strengths at 30°. A study of the dependence of stability constants on ionic strengths showed that

TABLE 1—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR THE FORMATION OF 1 : 1 AND 1 : 2 Fe^{2+} CHELATES AT 30° AND 0.1 M IONIC STRENGTH

Ligand	pK_a	Stability constant	$-\Delta G^\ddagger$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta H^\ddagger$ kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS J mol ⁻¹
2-(Phenylhydrazino)propionic acid	5.15	4.49 (3.53)	26.02 (20.45)	22.38 (18.24)	12.00 (7.28)
2-(<i>p</i> -Tolylhydrazino)propionic acid	5.42	4.56 (3.94)	26.44 (22.84)	22.50 (20.33)	12.97 (8.28)
2-(<i>p</i> -Nitrophenylhydrazino)propionic acid	4.53	3.42 (2.95)	19.83 (17.11)	17.44 (15.39)	7.86 (5.65)
2-(<i>o</i> -Tolylhydrazino)propionic acid	4.85	3.62 (3.20)	21.00 (18.53)	17.65 (16.52)	11.04 (6.61)

The figures in the parentheses indicate the stability constant and thermodynamic parameters for 1 : 2 complexes. The standard deviation of stability constants is ± 0.05 . The limit of error for log K values is ± 0.05 .

there is a regular and slow decrease in the values of stability constants with the increase in ionic strength, which is in agreement with the trend in the variation of pK_a values of above ligands. It is seen from Table 1 that the overall stability constants of Fe^{2+} chelates follow the order :

2-(*p*-nitrophenylhydrazino)propionic acid < 2-(*o*-tolylhydrazino)propionic acid < 2-(phenylhydrazino)propionic acid < 2-(*p*-tolylhydrazino)propionic acid.

The observed order is in accordance with the electron withdrawing property of nitro group and electron releasing effect of methyl group. The low stability constants observed in the case of 2-(*o*-tolylhydrazino)propionic acid with transition metal ions may be ascribed to steric factors.

Effect of temperature : The values of ΔH^\ddagger , ΔG^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger have been calculated from the stability constants obtained at various temperatures at constant ionic strength (0.1 M) using Gibbs-Helmholtz equation and are given in Table 1. The ΔH^\ddagger values were evaluated from the plots of log K

vs $1/T$. The positive slopes indicate that the reactions are exothermic. The ΔG^\ddagger values are negative for all the chelates showing that these reactions are spontaneous. The exothermic nature of reactions is supported by the negative values of ΔH^\ddagger . The ΔS^\ddagger values are positive for all the chelates showing that entropy is favourable for complex formation. The ΔG^\ddagger and ΔH^\ddagger were separated into their electrostatic (ΔG_e^\ddagger and ΔH_e^\ddagger) and cratic (ΔG_c^\ddagger and ΔH_c^\ddagger) components in order to know the extent of ionic and covalent nature of bonding in these complexes as suggested by Digischer and Nancollas¹⁴. Comparison of the electrostatic and cratic components of the thermodynamic parameters from Table 2 for the equilibrium (1)

indicates that ΔG_e^\ddagger values are significantly more negative than ΔG_c^\ddagger values. This trend suggests that non-electrostatic forces are stronger than the electrostatic forces in 1 : 1 chelates. The data for the equilibrium (2)

shows that the 1 : 1 complexes are more favourable than 1 : 2 complexes. Comparison of the difference in the electrostatic and cratic components of Fe^{2+} chelates with that of the other transition metal ion complexes reported earlier³, observes the following order

which may be due to the anomalous behaviour of stabilities of Fe^{2+} complexes.

Effect of dielectric constants on stabilities : Another important factor influencing the stability constants of metal chelates are the dielectric constant of the medium and solvating property of the solvent. An attempt has been made to investigate the effect of variation in dielectric constant on the stabilities of complexes of transition metal ions with above ligands in various ethanol-water mixtures (40, 50, 60 and 70%, v/v). The stability constants of the Fe^{2+} chelates in different percentages of ethanol-water mixtures are recorded in

TABLE 2—ELECTROSTATIC AND CRATIC COMPONENTS OF THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR THE FORMATION OF 1 : 1 AND 1 : 2 METAL CHELATES AT 0.1 M IONIC STRENGTH

Metal ion : Fe^{2+}	Values in kJ mol ⁻¹			
	Electrostatic components		Cratic components	
	$-\Delta G_e^\ddagger$	ΔH_e^\ddagger	$-\Delta G_c^\ddagger$	$-\Delta H_c^\ddagger$
2-(Phenylhydrazino)propionic acid	9.87 (8.87)	3.81 (3.43)	26.27 (21.71)	26.15 (21.63)
2-(<i>p</i> -Tolylhydrazino)propionic acid	10.08 (9.08)	3.93 (3.56)	26.53 (23.89)	26.35 (23.76)
2-(<i>p</i> -Nitrophenylhydrazino)propionic acid	9.04 (8.53)	3.47 (3.26)	21.00 (18.79)	20.83 (18.62)
2-(<i>o</i> -Tolylhydrazino)propionic acid	9.71 (8.74)	3.72 (3.39)	21.46 (19.99)	21.29 (19.83)

The figures in the parentheses indicate the values of electrostatic and cratic components for 1 : 2 complexes.

TABLE 3—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF Fe^{2+} CHELATES IN VARIOUS PERCENTAGES OF ETHANOL-WATER MIXTURES

Ligands	40%	50%	60%	70%
2-(Phenylhydrazino) propionic acid	4.49 (3.53)	4.70 (3.68)	4.92 (3.83)	5.13 (3.96)
2-(<i>p</i> -Tolyhydrazino propionic acid	4.56 (3.94)	4.85 (4.09)	5.07 (4.26)	5.34 (4.39)
2-(<i>p</i> -Nitrophenylhydrazino) propionic acid	3.42 (2.95)	3.58 (3.07)	3.76 (3.20)	3.91 (3.31)
2-(<i>o</i> -Tolyhydrazino) propionic acid	3.62 (3.20)	3.80 (3.34)	3.99 (3.47)	4.17 (3.60)

The figures in the parentheses indicate the values of $\log K_1$.

Table 3. The plots of $\log K_1$ vs $1/D$ are non-linear while the plots of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ vs mole fraction showed a good linear relationship. It is seen that with increase in the organic content of the solvent the stability constants increase. This is similar¹⁵ to the ligands containing O-metal links, the stabilities increased by an increase in the organic content of the solvent. However, the reported¹⁶ effect of solvent on complexes containing N-metal links concluded that the organic content of the solvent had little influence on the stabilities of complexes. In the present study of the complexes containing both O-metal and N-metal links the observed increase in the stabilities may be due to the O-metal link which is strongly affected¹⁷.

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